

Readability of Grade 7 English learning module

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ABSTRACT

Readability of a text determines the appropriateness of text to the grade reading level. I examined the readability of Grade 7 English learning module to find out if the text suits to the reader. I utilized the Fry Readability to test the complexity of text and the grade reading level. Inclusions with these readability tests are the sentence and word lengths which are variables used to check the readability of the text. I found out that the learning module is slightly not appropriate to the Grade 7 reading level because the text has used longer words that consequently made sentences long. Thus, if text contains words that are too long for a particular grade level, there is a reading difficulty.

Keywords: *english, Fry readability test, learning module*

I. INTRODUCTION

Proposition Theory on reading comprehension involves the reader in constructing a main idea (Gunning, 2006). A Reader can process the skill to achieve the highest level of comprehension when he or she formulates the main idea of that text. According Dayagbil (2009), one facet of reading can be constructive in which a reader constructs meaning from the printed page. Yet, she mentioned a text factor in reading which refers to the difficulty level of the material read, content, text structure, and style of writing. Regardless of the content, organization of texts and reader's purpose towards reading, I claim that the text contributes to his or her understanding.

The Board of Directors of the International Reading Association or IRA (1985) as cited by Pikulski (2012), reported that there are factors in identifying the readability of read materials, including the syntactic intricacy of sentences. This means that if this reason can be avoided, consequently, the reading material should be a big help in the understanding of the readers. Moreover, Chall and Dale (1995) concluded that the purpose of readability assessment is to realize

a "best match" between intended readers and texts. Additionally, Harris and Hodges (1995) pointed out that text and reader variables interact in determining the readability of any piece of material for any individual reader. It is how information from the text and the knowledge possessed by the reader get together to produce meaning (Anderson, 1985). Therefore, readability is finding balance between the reader's knowledge, which is comprehension, and the text itself. Thus, text facilitates the reader's understanding.

The Department of Education in the Philippines has recently implemented a new curriculum-the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum otherwise known as K to 12 (from Kindergarten to Grade 12) to the educational system. Its aim is to develop each Filipino and the overall social and economic progress of the country, and enhance students' abilities and skills that qualify for employability (Southeast Asian Ministry of Education Organization, 2012). Department of Education has designed a learning module that helps teachers and students put to life the learning outcomes. However, aside from

testing the comprehensibility of the module, I was determined to assess its readability.

Therefore, I examined the texts to see if they are readable for a particular grade reading level and to find out if the module suits the reader. I further understood that how well the authors of the learning module succeed depends on the readability of the text by using the Fry Readability Formula Test.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

William Gray identified four components of reading: (a) word perception; (b) comprehension; (c) reaction; and (d) integration. I considered word perception and reaction components to attach to the concept of readability. Word perception means that the reader perceives the word, once the reader reads, he or she must recognize the words, phrases and sentences, and reaction means that there is an interaction between the reader and the text (Simmons, 1965).

The study is anchored on the Fry Readability Formula which determines and analyzes the readability of the text. In this view, word perception and reaction components supported the concept on the Fry Readability Test. Hence, reading readability comes in if the text is easy-to-read and appropriate to the grade reader. A text is appropriate when the reading level is suited to the reader. Thus, the text must match that of what he or she reads. There are a lot of readability formulae, but I chose Fry Readability to manually check for its word and sentence structure provided with its formula and mechanics. Heydari (2012) investigated the validity of some better-known readability formulae: the SMOG Index of Readability, Flesch Reading Ease Readability Formula, Gunning's Fog-Index of Readability, and Flesch-Kincaid Formula. He correlated human evaluation versus readability formulae. Results suggested that there were no correlations between the two sets of evaluation. Thus, human judgments are needed to be considered as well.

Moreover, to assess a particular reading material, Fry (1968) developed one of the more popular reading formulae, the Fry Graph Readability Formula. He developed readability tests based on graph A *Readability Formula That Saves Time* (Journal of Reading, 1968). This graph-

based test determines readability of the printed text.

DuBay (2002) said that the documents' content, design, style of writing, and text shall account for if a text is "easy-to-read". So, he defined readability as how easy a reading text is to read or "reading ease". In a nutshell, the formula determines the complexity of text and grade reading level.

Text complexity is defined by the Common Core State Standards (2010) as three interrelated components: (a) Qualitative dimensions; (b) Quantitative dimensions; and (c) Reader and task considerations. I disregarded the qualitative dimensions because I did not delve on the reader's schemata in reading or his or her interest towards reading. I preferred to focus on the quantitative dimensions of text complexity which refer to aspects such as word length or frequency, sentence length, and text cohesion that are difficult for a human reader to evaluate efficiently, especially in long texts. Moreover, the third dimension is related to the study because it examines the perfect match between the reader and the task purpose and the complexity of the task assigned and the posed questions, must also be considered in determining whether a text is appropriate for a given student. However, text cohesion is excluded on how sentences are connected with one another.

Analysis of text involves the difficulty of the text, text structure, and author's style of writing. I considered text structure vis-à-vis the complexity of text. Anderson and Armbruster (1984) as cited by the Common Core State Standards (2010), recognized two features of texts: (a) text structure and (b) audience appropriateness. They said that text structure is the arrangement of related words and connecting ideas. Hence, the arrangement of text may lead to readers' comprehensibility from the printed text. Text structure facilitates reading comprehension. Thus, a well-structured text enables readers to understand main ideas and identify relevant information. So, readers will become proficient and aware of text structures, understand key points of ideas, and recollect the details of what was read, and the summary reflects on the text organization.

Hess (2006, 2008) reported that text structure is the organizational structure within paragraphs

and longer texts, suited to genre (literary and informational texts) and purpose (appropriate audience and levels). However, in the report of CCSSO (2010), text complexity included both qualitative and quantitative measures since a text requires reader's skills. Similarly, text depends on the readers. There is a difference between reading literary and informational texts. Reading the former for pleasure entails a different level of reading whereas, reading the latter necessitates informative level of reading. In other words, understanding depends on the purpose of reading.

This is not surprising given the degree to which level of reading the readers get its meaning not only depends on context, but on the complexity of text. If it is easy to understand how the words of a sentence relate to each other, readers are often able to figure out the meaning of particular words that are unfamiliar. Masson and Waldron (1994) identified two aspects of text structure: complexity (including length) and organization (word order), though they are examined separately. I focused on complexity that includes sentence and word lengths. But these aspects are intertwined to determine its complexity. The more ideas a sentence contains (complexity), the greater the temptation to depart from the way sentences are normally organized in order to make it clear how the ideas relate to each other. Hess and Biggam (2004) said that a text that has short simple sentences may be challenging if they contain abstract or vague ideas. So, it also needs a reader's skill to interpret. But in terms of readability, I argued with this idea because quantitatively, readability examines text complexity and level of readers regardless of what they understand. In the report of Hess (2011) about Tools for Examining Text Complexity, she mentioned that some text structures are more easily learned and understood before other more complex structures. This means that text should be written in short simple sentences.

To support, in a readability test, I considered the writer or author's diction in the text. Diction is the author's word choice in his or her work. When a writer or author thinks about diction, he or she is considering the word choice. It must be suited to the purpose of writing. Moreover, in terms of readability of text, the number of syllables in a

word is also relative to diction. Words can be monosyllabic or polysyllabic. Monosyllabic words can add emphasis to the point one is making, on the contrary, the more polysyllabic words, the more difficult the content. Also, be sure that the word a writer or author chooses has the correct connotation for what he or she is trying to say (Anson, Schweigler & Muth, 2010). CCSSO (2010) studied that average word length is measured as a factor in determining readability. Thus accordingly, if there are so many words in a sentence, chances are, the text may be difficult to read with comprehension.

To encapsulate text complexity, it encompasses sentence and word lengths. Chall, Bissex, Conard, and Harris-Sharples (1996) as cited by Hess and Biggam (2004), suggested that vocabulary words and sentence structures may be considered in determining appropriateness of text for a given grade reading level. Moreover, length of text affects the ability of students to sustain engagement with the text. That is why Fry (1968) determined this complexity by measuring the numbers of sentences and syllables in the text. After these measurements, one is able to identify the grade reading level.

I, through the sentence and word lengths, determined the grade reading levels in the Basic Education and College levels. These levels will identify to what level the text would be more appropriate. In the Philippines, the K to 12 Program covers Kindergarten and 12 years of basic education (six years of primary education, four years of Junior High School, and two years of Senior High School [SHS]) to provide sufficient time for mastery of concepts and skills, develop lifelong learners, and prepare graduates for tertiary education, middle-level skills development, employment, and entrepreneurship. So, I as well used the learning module of Grade 7 in English. This module is a supported curriculum which is used in the teaching-learning process. This serves as the guide for both teacher and students to realize learning outcomes.

The use of Fry Graph Readability Formula determines the learning module's readability. The National Partnership for Women & Families in 2009 reported that the Fry Readability Formula assigns an approximate grade reading level to a

passage of text. Applying the formula will help one decide how to edit the document so that it is more readable. The formula depends on the vocabulary and sentence structure of the text, not the content and organization. Heydari (2012) said that the results from using readability formulae provide the writer of the text with much needed information to reach his target audience.

On the good side of this, DuBay (2002) mentioned the remunerations in utilizing readability tests: (a) they are easy to use; (b) they encourage writers to use simple words and simple short sentences; (c) they serve as the starting point in crafting a text; and (d) they are used for editing when readability test is concern.

Inversely, there are restrictions in administering readability tests: (a) they do not measure the coherence of the text; (b) they do not measure if the text is ethnically and culturally appropriate; (c) they do not compute the reader's schemata; and (d) they do not measure the reader's willingness to read and learn.

Last of all, the Fry readability test has some special rules: sentences end with a period (.), an exclamation point (!), a semicolon (;), a question mark (?), a colon (:), or a comma (,); hyphenated words count as one word; count proper nouns; numbers are not counted; count abbreviations as their original whole word; and count lists as one sentence each if items are separated by commas (,) or semicolons (;). Lists with full sentences (like this one) count for as many sentences as are in the list.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a Descriptive Method which is used as a way of presenting facts and other data concerning the nature and status of anything that may be included in the research investigation, and Minitab to statistically treat the data of the learning module in English for Grade 7 designed by the Learning Area Team Languages and Multiliteracies of the Department of Education in the Philippines. Particularly, the module is labeled into four quarter parts: 1st quarter, 2nd quarter, 3rd quarter and 4th quarter. The module has only 13 short stories from Philippine literature that can be read in the 1st and 2nd quarters. The 3rd and 4th quarters do not have short stories. Thus, I took

Figure 1: The Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework

all 13 short stories that would be used in the study. Therefore, Fry Graph Readability Formula is used to test the text if it is readable and appropriate to the reader and his or her grade reading level.

In this phase, the gathered data are presented, analyzed, and interpreted using the Fry Graph Readability Formula. The following shows that steps in getting the average number of sentences and syllables for the 13 stories. I: Step 1: Selected three (3) samples of 100-word text of passages randomly (eliminate the numbers from word count); Step 2: Counted accurately the 100 words for each passage, beginning at the start of a sentence. If the final word does not fall at the end of a sentence, estimate the length of words counted with a fraction of the whole sentence (estimating the fraction of the last sentence to the nearest 1/10th); Step 3: Counted the syllable length in all three 100-word passages; Step 4: Found the mean of the sentence length from each passage; Step 5: Found the mean syllable length in each passage; and Step 6: Entered the graph with average sentence length and number of syllables.

The Fry readability graph displays the average length of sentences and syllables. An area where a dot is situated signifies the approximate reading grade level of the content. The author or writer of the reading text will find the mean word length (number of syllables) on the horizontal axis and the mean sentence length (number of words) on the vertical axis. The crossing of the two points will fall in a section showing the grade reading level. The grade level of the text may be indicated through the numbers in between of the straight lines are where a dot is plotted. The curve represents a normal text. Points below the

curve imply longer than average sentence lengths. Likewise, points above the curve represent text with a more difficult vocabulary but shorter sentence lengths.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following data were tabulated and statistically treated for easier discussion of the results. The tables are presented to show the computations of the average number of sentences and syllables per text. The graph shows the results of the counted syllable and sentence lengths the Fry Readability Graph Formula from the 1st, 2nd and 3rd 100 words of the 13 short stories in the 1st and 2nd quarters. In addition, each short story must have two sets of discussions and interpretations: one for the table and one for the Fry graph.

Table 1.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result (The Origin of This World-Maranao)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	12	163
Second 100 words	7	140
Third 100 words	7	130
Σ	26	406
\bar{X}	8.67	144.33

Table 1 shows the number of sentences and the number of syllables from the first to third 100 words. Based on the computed table, the graph displays that dot is located above the normal standard readability curve. This goes to show that the text has a high frequency of words. There are readability formulae that measure the word and sentence lengths because they are factors in determining students' reading ability. CCSSO (2010) informed that if there are so many words in a sentence chances are, the text may be difficult to read with comprehension. If this happens, the learning module may not be read appropriately by Grade 7 that consequently leads to failure to reading proficiency.

Graph 1. The Readability Test Result

Table 2.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result (How The World Was Created)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	5	125
Second 100 words	5	150
Third 100 words	5	131
Σ	15	406
\bar{X}	5	132.33

Graph 2. The Readability Test Result

Table 2 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is located slightly below the normal standard readability curve. This goes to show that the text has long sentences that

lead to the complexity of text. It is almost situated on the Grade 8 reading level. In other words, the module can be intricately read by Grade 7 students. Hess (2011) mentioned that some text structures are more easily learned and understood before other more complex structures. This means that text should be written in short simple sentences.

Table 3.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result (Samal Genesis)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	5	136
Second 100 words	5	136
Third 100 words	8	145
Σ	18	417
\bar{X}	6	139

Graph 3. The Readability Test Result

Table 3 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the average number of sentence lengths is 6 and the average number of syllable lengths is 139. The dot is located above the normal standard readability curve. The text falls on the complexity of text in terms of the word length of frequency. This means that the text has long and complex words that may not lead readers to reading proficiency. Words affect reading comprehension. A word is label for an internal reality which helps create a new perception. The

richer one's vocabulary, the greater his or her reading power becomes (Anderson & Freebody, 1981). However, CCSSO (2010) informed that if there are so many words in a sentence chances are, the text may be difficult to read with comprehension. The learning module should use simple basic words for Grade 7 reading level.

Table 4.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result (Why the Sky is High)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	6	122
Second 100 words	7	141
Third 100 words	7	129
Σ	20	392
\bar{X}	6.67	130.67

Graph 4. The Readability Test Result

Table 4 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is located above the normal standard readability curve. This means that the text is slightly not readable for the Grade 7. Interestingly, the red dot is located on the Grade 6 level of readability. This implies that there is a mismatched of the appropriate grade reading level and the text. Furthermore, Chall and Dale (1995) concluded that the purpose of readability assessment is to realize a "best match" between intended reader and text. Harris and

Hodges (1995) pointed out that text and reader variables interact in determining the readability of any material. The learning module can be read if it uses simple basic words, thus, readers can not only learn vocabulary but also comprehend the meaning of text it offers.

Table 5.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result (Ibalon)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	8	140
Second 100 words	6	138
Third 100 words	7	136
Σ	21	414
\bar{X}	7	138

Graph 5. The Readability Test Result

Table 5 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is located in the suited grade reading level that is Grade 7. However, the red dot is above the normal standard readability curve which means the text is readable; however, it contains long words. CCSSO (2010), stated in the report that text complexity like word length or frequency, contributes to the difficulty of the text. Thus, the text may be difficult, if not impossible, for a human reader to evaluate efficiently, especially in long texts. Further, CCSSO (2010) informed that if there are so many words

in a sentence, chances are the text may be difficult to read with comprehension. The learning module should use simple basic words for Grade 7 reading level.

Table 6.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result (Indarapatra and Sulayman)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	5	164
Second 100 words	4	134
Third 100 words	4	132
Σ	13	430
\bar{X}	4.67	143.33

Graph 6. The Readability Test Result

Table 6 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. Interestingly, the graph displays that the dot is located on the normal standard readability curve which means that the text is a normal text. This means that the text should be readable and supposedly suitable to its intended readers. However, the text is not suited to the Grade 7 reading level because the dot lies on the Grade 9 level. Harris and Hodges (1995) pointed out that text and reader variables interact in determining the readability of any piece of material for any individual reader. Readability is a match between the reader and the text. CCSSO (2010) reported that how the text acts upon the reader is as important as how the reader acts upon the text.

Table 7.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(The Story of Lam-ang [A Summary])

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	8	137
Second 100 words	7	139
Third 100 words	7	140
Σ	22	416
\bar{X}	7.33	138.67

Table 8.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(The Centipede)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	6	164
Second 100 words	8	130
Third 100 words	11	140
Σ	25	385
\bar{X}	8.33	128.33

Graph 7. The Readability Test Result

Table 7 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is located above the normal standard readability curve which means the text contains vocabulary words. CCSSO (2010) informed that if there are so many words in a sentence chances are, the text may be difficult to read with comprehension. In addition, Chall et al. (1996) suggested that vocabulary structure is needed as well in determining appropriateness of text for a given grade reading level. If this happens, the learning module may not be read appropriately by Grade 7 and thus consequently leads to failure to reading proficiency. Therefore, the learning module should use simple basic words for Grade 7 reading level.

Graph 8. The Readability Test Result

Table 8 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is located above the normal standard readability curve. It falls on the baseline between Grades 4 and 5. This means that the text can be read (readable) by Grade 7 readers but not suited to their reading level. Based on the result, the researcher concludes that the text is not suited to Grade 7. There is a mismatch of the text and the reader. Readability is a balance between the reader and the text. There is no balance because the learning module uses longer words. If this happens, the learning module may not be read appropriately by Grade 7 which consequently leads to a failure to reading proficiency. Therefore, the learning module should use simple basic words for Grade 7 reading level.

Table 9.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(The Mats)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	6	153
Second 100 words	8	163
Third 100 words	9	129
Σ	23	445
\bar{X}	7.67	148.33

Graph 9. The Readability Test Result

Table 9 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The dot is situated very far from the normal standard readability curve. This means that the text may contain longer words. CCSSO (2010) informed that if there are so many words in a sentence chances are, the text may be difficult to read with comprehension. Furthermore, the dot is almost placed on the Grade 8 reading level. This means that the vocabulary words may be unfamiliar by the readers. Simple words to be used for an appropriate reading level are considerable in the complexity of text. Similarly Table 8, there is no balance because the learning module uses longer words. If this happens, the learning module may not be read appropriately by Grade 7 which consequently leads to decreased to reading proficiency. Therefore, the learning module should use simple basic words for Grade 7 reading level.

Table 10.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(How My Brother Leon Brought Home A Wife)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	10	132
Second 100 words	11	125
Third 100 words	8	125
Σ	29	382
\bar{X}	9.67	127.33

Graph 10. The Readability Test Result

Table 10 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is located above the normal standard readability curve. This means that the text is highly not in a normal text. The text is complex because it may have long or unfamiliar words. CCSSO (2010) informed that if there are so many words in a sentence chances are, the text may be difficult to read with comprehension.

Surprisingly, the red dot is located within the Grade 4 reading level. In other words, the text is not suited to the reading level for Grade 7 but readable. This implies that there is a mismatch of between the appropriate grade reading level and the text. Furthermore, Chall and Dale (1995) concluded that the purpose of readability assessment is to realize a “best match” between intended readers and texts.

Table 11.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(Wedding Dance)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	8	130
Second 100 words	6	127
Third 100 words	7	122
Σ	21	379
\bar{X}	7	126.33

Table 12.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(The Bread of Salt)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	5	132
Second 100 words	6	116
Third 100 words	4	130
Σ	15	378
\bar{X}	5	126

Graph 11. The Readability Test Result

Table 11 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is slightly placed above the normal standard readability curve with the average number of sentence lengths based on the table. This means that the text is readable for the Grade 7 but not suited to the grade reading level. This implies that there is a mismatched of the level and the text. There is no balance because the learning module uses longer words. If this happens, the learning module may not be read appropriately by Grade 7 which consequently leads to decreased failure to reading proficiency. Therefore, the learning module should use simple basic words for Grade 7 reading level.

Graph 12. The Readability Test Result

Table 12 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is situated below the normal standard readability curve. This means that the text may contain longer sentences. There should be a balance of the complexity of text structure. Hess (2010, 2011) mentioned that some text structures are more easily learned and understood before other more complex structures. This means that text should be written in short simple sentences.

Table 13.
Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result
(The Baby in the Bottle)

Dimensions	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
First 100 words	4	123
Second 100 words	4	132
Third 100 words	5	128
Σ	13	383
\bar{X}	4.33	127.67

Graph 13. The Readability Test Result

Table 13 shows the counted syllable and sentence lengths from the first to third 100 words. The graph displays that the dot is situated below the normal standard readability curve. This means that the text is readable but has longer sentences. The IRA Board of Directors reported that many factors enter into determining the readability of materials, including the syntactic complexity of sentences. Hess (2010, 2011) mentioned that some text structures are more easily learned and understood before other more complex structures. This means that text should be written in short simple sentences. Lastly, if these reasons can be avoided, consequently, the reading material should be a big help in readers' understanding.

Table 14.
The Summary on the Average Number of Sentences and Syllables Result of the 13 Short Story in the Learning Module

Short Story	Number of Sentences	Number of Syllables
1	8.67	144.33
2	5	135.33
3	6*	139*
4	6.67*	130.67*
5	7*	138*
6	4.67	143.33
7	7.33*	138.67*
8	8.33	128.33
9	7.67	148.33
10	9.67	127.33
11	7	126.33
12	5	126
13	4.33	127.67
Σ	87.34	1753.32
\bar{X}	6.718	134.87
Lower Limit	5.800	130.61
Upper Limit	7.636	139.13
SE (Mean)	0.459	2.13

Graph 14. The Readability Test Result

The table displays the average syllable and sentence lengths of the 13 short stories in the Grade 7 Learning Module in English from quarters 1 and 2. I computed its mean to get the large sample size. Through this, the lower and upper limits were computed to determine the parameters of graph whether the text is a normal text. Lastly, the Standard Error Mean quantified how precise the parameters of limits is to tell if the text is readable or not.

For the average number of sentence length, the lower and upper limits articulate that the text is readable when the dot is situated between 5.800 and 7.636. While for the average number of word length, the parameters indicate that the text is readable when the dot is placed between 130.61 and 139.13 in the Fry Readability Graph.

Among the 13 short stories, there are only four (4) texts that the results of the number of sentences and syllables are in between the parameters of a readable text. These stories are with asterisks: three (3), four (4), five (5) and seven (7). However, only story four (4) is not suited to the Grade 7 reading level. This goes to show that these asterisked number stories are readable to the Grade 7 students, thus, understanding of the text may be evident because the texts are readable. However, the fourth story is not suited to the reading level of the Grade 7 students. In other words, the text should be reviewed to make it readable and appropriate to the level of the readers. If this happens, aside from the text being readable, it is then easy for the readers specifically to the Grade 7 students to read the stories with comprehension. Thus, accordingly, if the texts are not catered to the intended audience, the reading texts also fail to let the readers understand its message. There should be a best match between the text and the readers. Based on the graph, the red dot is situated on the baseline between Grade 6 and 7 reading levels. This means that the text can be read and understood by both levels.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings suggest that longer words make the text difficult. If longer words are found in a text and are read by Grade 7, then there is a reading difficulty and an inappropriateness of the target grade reading level. Therefore, the English learning

module is readable but not appropriate to the grade 7 reading level. Thus, using Fry Readability formula validates the assumption on the difficulty of the Grade 7 English learning module. Ultimately, authors and writers must consider their reading audience. I further understand that on how well the authors of the learning module succeed depends on the readability of the text by using the Fry Graph Readability Formula.

Originality Index:	92 %
Similarity Index:	8 %
Paper ID:	664813027
Grammarly:	Checked

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